

DISCOVERY OF SOFTWARE INNOVATIONS USING REPOSITORY MINING

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BACKGROUND AND OBJECTIVES

Software version control platforms such as GitHub host millions of open-source software repositories. Due to the diversity of such projects and the public availability of data, these platforms are an appealing realm for discovering previously unseen technology trends, thereby fostering collaboration among programmers and researchers. To this end, advanced search tools are necessary to explore the vast amount of available information. Users can already explore repositories by searching via keyword queries, which fetch seemingly shallow results. Furthermore, collaboration in software development platforms has been supported by recommendation systems focusing on similarities between repositories. Keyword search and similarity-based recommendation are valuable means for exploring related projects in one's area of expertise, but are of limited use for discovering something new which can inspire new trends. Instead, innovations in technology often emerge from the synthesis of existing solutions in novel ways.

This contribution presents an approach to identifying synergies between software projects using text mining and network analysis techniques, which exploits not only their similarities but also their complementary features. The idea is inspired by Literature-Based-Discovery (LBD) [1], which was originally developed to uncover implicit knowledge in scientific literature databases by identifying new associations between scientific terms. In this work we adapt the concept of LBD to software project descriptions available on GitHub in order to discover potential synergies. Synergy between two software repositories is given if one can benefit from the other. In the example in Figure 1, repository *A* has two features: (1) “*pre-process data for significance tests*” and (2) “*conduct significance tests*”. Repository *B*, in contrast, has feature (2) and an additional feature: (3) “*conduct post-hoc analysis*”. As we see, these two repositories complement each other because they share a common feature, and each is missing one feature from the other: Repository *A* can benefit from Repository *B* and vice versa. Accordingly, we ask the question: How can one discover repositories that are similar to some extent but different enough to expand each other's functionality.

METHODS

The workflow consists of three sequential steps: (1) We extract software characteristics from the repositories' *readme* files using natural language processing techniques. We use *READMEClassifier* [2] to distinguish *readme* content describing the main software features from other sections.

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Figure 1: Two repositories are related by a common set of features. There is a potential synergy since both can extend the feature set of the other

(2) We characterize software projects using topic modeling algorithms. As a result each project is associated to one or more topics (representing software features), which can be modelled as a weighted bipartite network of software projects and features as shown in Figure 1. (3) We then determine pairs of software projects that can potentially benefit from each other via restricted random walks on the network resulting from Step 2. We configure the random walker such that starting at a repository *A*, it is more likely to end at a repository *B*, if both have some features in common (similarity) but in addition each single repository can contribute distinguishing features that few other projects have combined before (potential trend).

RESULTS

We evaluated this approach on more than 13K GitHub (open-source) Python project repositories. Skilled annotators evaluated the synergy between the repositories suggested by the proposed model as well as sets of random pairs of repositories. The results show that the developed models are significantly better at discovering synergies between software projects than random pairing at $p < 0.001$ with a medium effect size r . In addition we could show that our described methodology even re-discovered connections between software projects based on the developers' bookmarking activities (GitHub's stargazing feature).

REFERENCES

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